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Antidiabetic, Hypolipidaemic, Hepatorenal Protective and Antioxidant Effects of Locally Formulated Functional Diets in Alloxan-Induced Diabetic Wistar Rats

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Abstract

Diabetes mellitus is characterized by hyperglycaemia, oxidative stress, dyslipidaemia, and progressive hepatic and renal dysfunction. This study evaluated the antidiabetic, hepatoprotective, nephroprotective, hypolipidaemic, and antioxidant effects of locally formulated diets prepared from unripe plantain (*Musa paradisiaca*), soybean (*Glycine max*), tignut (*Cyperus esculentus*), and dates (*Phoenix dactylifera*) in alloxan-induced diabetic Wistar rats. Seven composite diets (A–G) were administered for 28 days. Fifty-five rats were assigned to eleven groups of five animals each. Groups 1–7 received diets A–G, group 8 received commercial soybean flour, group 9 received metformin, while groups 10 and 11 served as diabetic and normal controls, respectively. Biochemical analyses assessed liver and kidney function, serum electrolytes, lipid profile, and oxidative stress markers. Untreated diabetic rats showed elevated AST, ALT, ALP, urea, creatinine, total cholesterol, triglycerides, LDL, and VLDL levels, with reduced HDL and antioxidant enzyme activities relative to normal controls. The formulated diets significantly improved these parameters. Diet C produced notable improvements in renal and oxidative stress markers, including GSH ($1.42 \pm 0.16 \mu\text{mol/g}$ tissue), GPx ($0.06 \pm 0.00 \text{ U/mg}$ protein), and CAT ($3.58 \pm 0.44 \text{ U/mg}$ protein). The diets restored electrolyte balance and improved liver synthetic function, demonstrating protective effects against diabetes-induced biochemical alterations.

Keywords: Diabetes mellitus; Functional diets; Oxidative stress; Wistar rats.

1. INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus is one of the most prevalent endocrine and metabolic disorders globally, characterized by chronic hyperglycaemia resulting from impaired insulin secretion, insulin action, or both. Persistent hyperglycaemia is associated with several metabolic abnormalities including dyslipidaemia, oxidative stress, hepatic dysfunction, nephropathy, and electrolyte imbalance (American Diabetes Association, 2023). The International Diabetes Federation estimated that approximately 537 million adults were living with diabetes worldwide in 2021, with projections suggesting continued increases in prevalence over the coming decades (IDF, 2021).

Oxidative stress plays a central role in the pathogenesis and progression of diabetic complications. Hyperglycaemia promotes excessive generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), leading to lipid peroxidation, protein oxidation, DNA damage, and impairment of endogenous antioxidant systems

(Maritim et al., 2003). These oxidative alterations contribute significantly to hepatic injury, renal dysfunction, and cardiovascular complications commonly associated with diabetes mellitus.

Current management strategies for diabetes include insulin therapy, oral hypoglycaemic agents, and dietary modifications. However, prolonged use of synthetic drugs is often associated with adverse effects and high treatment costs, especially in developing countries (Ezeani et al., 2020). Consequently, there is increasing interest in the development of functional foods from indigenous plant materials capable of providing both nutritional and therapeutic benefits.

Unripe plantain (*Musa paradisiaca*) possesses low glycaemic properties and contains resistant starch, dietary fibre, vitamins, minerals, and antioxidant phytochemicals that may improve glycaemic regulation (Eleazu et al., 2013). Soybean (*Glycine max*) is rich in high-quality proteins, essential amino acids, and isoflavones with demonstrated antidiabetic and antioxidant effects (Messina, 2016). Tigernut (*Cyperus esculentus*) contributes dietary fibre, healthy fatty acids, and micronutrients, while dates (*Phoenix dactylifera*) are rich sources of phenolic compounds and natural antioxidants (Baliga et al., 2011).

The combination of these locally available food materials into composite functional diets may provide affordable and nutritionally beneficial alternatives for managing diabetes and its associated complications. Therefore, this study evaluated the effects of locally formulated diets from unripe plantain, soybean, tigernut, and dates on biochemical parameters in alloxan-induced diabetic Wistar rats.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Source of Food Materials and Identification

Plantain (*Musa paradisiaca*), Tigernut (*Cyperus esculentus Lativum*), Soybean (*Glycine max (L)Merrill*) and Date fruits (*Phoenix dactylifera*) were purchased from the local Municipal market in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigerian and were properly identified by Dr. Ekeke, Chimezie at the Reference Herbarium for Research and Germplasm Conservation, Department of Plant Science and Biotechnology, Faculty of Science, University of Port Harcourt.

2.2 Processing of Food Materials into Flour

2.2.1. Preparation of defatted soybean flour

The soybean flour was processed as described by Ijarotimi and Owoeye (2017). Soybean were thoroughly cleaned and oven dried in hot-air oven (Plus11 Sanyo Gallenkamp PLC, Loughborough, Leicestershire, UK) at 55°C for 12 h, milled (Laboratory blender (Model KM 901D; Kenwood Electronic, Hertfordshire, UK) and sieved through no 200 mm wire mesh sieve (British Standard) to obtain soybean flour. The flour was packed in a plastic container, sealed and stored at room temperature (~27°C) until required for use.

2.2.2. Processing of tigernut flour.

Tigernut tuber was processed into flour using the method of Oladele and Aina (2017) with slight modification. Yellow tigernut tubers were sorted to remove unwanted materials like stones, pebbles and other foreign seeds, washed with double distilled water and drained. The tubers were oven dried at 60°C for 20 h using a hot-air oven (Plus11 Sanyo Gallenkamp PLC, Loughborough, Leicestershire, UK), milled with a laboratory blender (Model KM 901D; Kenwood Electronic, Hertfordshire, UK) and passed through a 60 mm mesh sieve (British Standard) to obtain tigernut tuber flour. The flour was packed in a plastic container, sealed and stored at room temperature (~27°C) until analysis.

2.2.3. Processing of plantain flour

The plantain flour was processed using methods described by (Happi Emaga et al., 2007; Falade and Oyeyinka, 2015; Mepba et al. 2007) with slight modification. Fresh mature unripe plantains were sorted, washed thoroughly, and processed together with their peels to produce the flour. The plantains were manually peeled, and both the edible pulp and the peels were retained, cleaned, and sliced into thin uniform pieces. The slices were treated briefly in a mild anti-browning solution, drained, and dried in a hot-air oven at 50–60°C until a constant weight was obtained. The dried pulp and peel samples were then milled together into fine flour and sieved to obtain uniform particle size. The resulting composite flour, which contained both the plantain pulp and peel, was packaged in airtight containers and stored for subsequent analysis and diet formulation.

2.2.4. Processing of dates flour

The date flour was processed using method described by Peter Ikechukwu et al. (2020) with slight modification. Firstly, dates were washed with clean running water to remove any adhering dirt and contaminants. Afterwards, the dates were de-seeded manually by cutting the date fruit. Date pulp and the pericarp portion were placed in a drying oven for 6 h at 70 °C. After drying, the obtained date pulp in dried form was milled by a hand milling machine (Mechtech 357 R, Pakistan) and ground to fine homogenized powder through a mesh sieve (0.35 mm). Then, the obtained powder was stored in a food-grade bag at ambient temperature.

2.3. Formulations of food samples:

The plantain, tigernut tubers, date fruits and defatted soybean flour were blended with reference to 50% recommended daily intakes (RDI) of protein (56 g/day) and fat (20 g/day) for diabetes patient's adult using material balance equations. This was done in order to compensate for carbohydrate reduction, and also to maintain the energy value of the product for the target population. The following food combinations were thereafter obtained, that is, [A (plantain 59.46%, defatted soybean 30.54%, dates 10%), B (tigernut 54.83, defatted soybean 35.17% and dates 10%); C (plantain 46.07, tigernut, 11.50, defatted soybean, 32.43% and dates 10%); D (tigernuts 90%, dates 10%); E (plantain 90%, dates 10%); F (100% plantain with peels); G (100% plantain without peels)

2.4 Procurement and Management of Experimental Animals

Fifty five (55) wistar rats (*Rattus norvegicus*) of both sex weighing between 120 and 180g were obtained from Ogie integrated farms Aba, Abia State and were kept in the animal house of the Pharmacology Department, Basic Medical Science, University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State Nigeria. They were kept in an environment of normal ambient temperature and lighting was allowed for about 12 hours daily and the relative humidity of 40-60%. They were housed in metabolic cages, provided with clean drinking water and fed (vital feed Nigeria). Ethical conditions governing the conduct of experiments with life animals were strictly followed.

2.4.1 Statement of Animal Rights:

The study protocol was approved by the Research Ethics Committee for Research Management and Development of University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria. The experiments on wistar rats were conducted in accordance with the force laws and regulations as regards animal use and care as contained in the Canadian Council on Animal Care Guidelines and Protocol Review (CCAC [Canadian Council on Animal Care] 1993).

2.5 Induction of Diabetes

Diabetes was induced using intravenous alloxan (Sigma Co, USA) at a dose of 42 mg/kg of body weight into tail veins. Only rats with clinical signs of severe diabetes and fasting glucose \geq 250 mg/dL in two successive determinations (1 and 2 weeks after diabetes induction) were used. Diabetic rats that died during the postinduction period or at follow-up were replaced to avoid compromising the final number of rats in the sample.

2.6 Experimental Design

The rats were divided into eleven experimental groups of five rats per group. The rats in groups one to seven were fed on the formulated diets A to G respectively while rats in group eight and nine were fed on the soybean based commercial flour and Metformin (an antidiabetic drug) respectively. Groups ten and eleven serves as diabetic control (DC) and normal control (NC) respectively.

2.7 Collection of Blood Sample

At the end of the experimental period, the animals were fasted overnight with access to water ad libitum and sacrificed under chloroform anaesthesia. Blood samples were collected via cardiac puncture into heparinised and non-heparinised tubes. Serum was obtained by centrifugation at $3000 \times g$ for 25 minutes and used for biochemical analyses.

2.8 Determination of Biochemical Parameters.

Biochemical analyses were carried out using standard enzymatic spectrophotometric methods. Liver function parameters including aspartate aminotransferase (AST), alanine aminotransferase (ALT), alkaline phosphatase (ALP), total protein, albumin, and bilirubin were determined using assay kits

obtained from Fortress Diagnostics. Kidney function indices and serum electrolytes, including urea, creatinine, sodium (Na⁺), potassium (K⁺), chloride (Cl⁻), and bicarbonate (HCO₃⁻), were determined using assay kits sourced from Spectrum Diagnostics and Atlas Medical. Lipid profile parameters, including total cholesterol (TC), triglycerides (TG), high-density lipoprotein (HDL), low-density lipoprotein (LDL), and very low-density lipoprotein (VLDL), were analysed using assay kits obtained from Fortress Diagnostics. Oxidative stress markers were also evaluated. Reduced glutathione (GSH) was determined using the method described by Sedlak and Lindsay (1968). Glutathione peroxidase (GPx) activity was determined according to the method of Paglia and Valentine (1967), while catalase (CAT) activity was assayed using the method described by Aebi (1984).

2.9 Statistical Analysis

Data were subjected to analysis of variance using SPSS (IBM version. 20.0, SPSS Inc., Quarry Bay, Hong Kong) and presented as means (\pm SEM). Comparisons between different groups were done using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT). Values of $p < 0.05$ were considered as statistically significant as described by Talha Yalta (2008).

3. RESULTS

3.1 Effects of Formulated Diets on Liver Function Parameters of Diabetic Wistar Rats

Table 3.1 presents the effects of the formulated diets, control diet, and metformin on liver function indices of diabetic wistar rats. The untreated diabetic group showed significant elevations in AST (140.68 ± 0.47 U/L), ALT (110.66 ± 2.04 U/L), and ALP (180.53 ± 0.43 U/L) compared with the normal control group. Total protein and albumin levels were markedly reduced in the diabetic control group. Treatment with the formulated diets significantly reduced serum AST, ALT, and ALP levels relative to the untreated diabetic group. Rats fed Diet E showed relatively improved total protein (73.58 ± 0.64 g/L) and albumin (47.52 ± 0.56 g/L) levels. Bilirubin concentrations were also reduced among treated groups, indicating restoration of liver integrity.

3.2 Effects of Formulated Diets on Kidney Function and Serum Electrolytes of Diabetic Wistar Rats

Table 3.2 presents the effects of the formulated diets, control diet, and metformin on renal function markers and serum electrolytes. The untreated diabetic rats exhibited elevated urea (10.61 ± 0.67 mmol/L) and creatinine (120.29 ± 4.20 μ mol/L) levels compared with treated and control groups. Electrolyte imbalance was also evident, with reduced sodium, chloride, and bicarbonate levels and elevated potassium concentration. Administration of the formulated diets significantly improved renal function parameters and restored electrolyte balance. Diet C notably reduced urea concentration to 3.88 ± 1.04 mmol/L, while Diet D produced the lowest creatinine level (71.54 ± 16.55 μ mol/L).

3.3 Effects of Formulated Diets on Lipid Profile of Diabetic Wistar Rats

Table 3.4 presents effects of formulated on the lipid profile of diabetic wistar rats. The diabetic control group showed marked dyslipidaemia characterized by elevated total cholesterol (3.75 ± 0.14 mmol/L), triglycerides (2.89 ± 0.07 mmol/L), LDL (2.50 ± 0.14 mmol/L), and VLDL (0.82 ± 0.15 mmol/L), alongside reduced HDL (0.50 ± 0.06 mmol/L). Treatment with the formulated diets significantly improved lipid profiles. Diet E recorded the lowest total cholesterol (1.37 ± 0.26 mmol/L) and LDL (0.83 ± 0.13 mmol/L), while Diet B showed the highest HDL value (1.64 ± 0.26 mmol/L).

3.4 Effects of Formulated Diets on Oxidative Stress Markers of Diabetic Wistar Rats

Table 3.4 presents the impact of the formulated diets, control diet and metformin on oxidative stress markers. The untreated diabetic group demonstrated significant oxidative stress evidenced by reduced GSH (0.40 ± 0.13 μ mol/g tissue), GPx (0.03 ± 0.02 U/mg protein), and CAT (1.15 ± 0.45 U/mg protein) activities. Treatment with the formulated diets significantly enhanced antioxidant enzyme activities. Diet C showed elevated GSH (1.42 ± 0.16 μ mol/g tissue) and CAT (3.58 ± 0.44 U/mg protein) levels, while Diet E also demonstrated strong antioxidant activity with CAT value of 3.50 ± 0.33 U/mg protein.

Table 3.1 Effects of Formulated Diets on Liver Function Parameters of Diabetic Wistar Rats

Groups	AST (u/l)	ALT (u/l)	ALP (u/l)	T.P (g/L)	ALB (g/L)	T.B (μmol/L)	C.B (umol/l)
1	46.68±0.47 ^b	30.66±2.04 ^b	54.53±0.43 ^b	65.25±0.45 ^c	38.78±0.69 ^c	8.39±0.33 ^b	4.42±0.23 ^b
2	40.20±1.79 ^c	28.32±1.69 ^b	50.49±0.55 ^c	67.20±1.73 ^c	41.58±0.41 ^c	8.85±0.51 ^b	4.06±0.27 ^b
3	37.91±0.42 ^c	28.63±2.17 ^b	52.69±0.66 ^c	69.74±0.65 ^c	44.52±0.64 ^b	8.59±0.29 ^b	3.71±0.26 ^b
4	38.18±2.02 ^c	31.23±0.51 ^b	46.80±0.68 ^c	65.47±0.48 ^c	42.55±0.63 ^c	7.20±0.35 ^b	3.53±0.14 ^b
5	37.38±2.39 ^c	26.92±0.61 ^b	45.82±0.47 ^c	73.58±0.64 ^a	47.52±0.56 ^a	9.31±0.54 ^b	3.55±0.22 ^b
6	36.78±2.42 ^c	33.71±2.51 ^b	51.75±0.56 ^c	71.67±0.38 ^c	46.71±0.74 ^a	7.84±0.25 ^b	4.28±0.22 ^b
7	38.28±2.27 ^c	29.17±2.45 ^b	48.69±0.54 ^c	67.95±2.04 ^c	38.59±0.23 ^c	7.10±1.83 ^b	4.20±0.26 ^b
8	41.80±2.20 ^c	33.22±3.45 ^b	48.75±0.58 ^c	72.15±0.26 ^a	44.35±0.50 ^b	9.79±0.19 ^b	3.30±0.12 ^b
9	37.91±0.42 ^c	28.63±2.17 ^b	52.69±0.66 ^c	69.74±0.65 ^c	44.52±0.64 ^b	8.59±0.29 ^b	3.71±0.26 ^b
10	140.68±0.47 ^a	110.66±2.04 ^a	180.53±0.43 ^a	45.25±0.45 ^d	28.78±0.69 ^d	24.39±0.33 ^a	10.42±0.23 ^a
11	38.18±2.02 ^a	31.23±0.51 ^b	46.80±0.68 ^c	65.47±0.48 ^c	42.55±0.63 ^c	7.20±0.35 ^b	3.53±0.14 ^c

Means (±SEM) with different alphabetical superscripts in the same column are significantly different at P < 0.05.

Table 3.2. Effect of Formulated Diets on Kidney Function and Serum Electrolytes of Diabetic Wistar Rats.

Group	UR (mmol/L)	CR (μmol/L)	K (mmol/L)	Na (mmol/L)	Cl (mmol/L)	HCO ₃ (mmol/L)
1	5.65±0.60 ^c	101.59±4.64 ^c	4.52±0.24 ^b	136.25±0.32 ^b	102.00±1.00 ^a	21.98±0.49 ^c
2	6.33±0.15 ^b	105.66±5.55 ^b	4.00±0.10 ^d	132.02±0.41 ^c	98.00±1.41 ^b	25.48±0.57 ^b
3	3.88±1.04 ^d	102.60±4.68 ^c	4.31±0.16 ^c	138.44±2.47 ^a	98.00±1.00 ^b	27.79±0.57 ^a
4	3.53±0.15 ^d	71.54±16.55 ^f	4.02±0.24 ^d	134.92±0.60 ^b	98.00±1.41 ^b	23.50±0.27 ^c
5	6.31±0.24 ^b	95.22±3.52 ^d	4.58±0.13 ^b	135.02±0.67 ^b	98.00±1.00 ^b	27.20±0.29 ^a
6	6.38±0.19 ^a	93.10±4.04 ^h	4.14±0.09 ^d	132.46±0.41 ^c	98.00±1.41 ^b	21.88±0.33 ^c
7	5.32±0.67 ^c	97.72±5.17 ^d	4.34±0.16 ^c	139.86±1.95 ^a	98.00±1.79 ^b	24.98±0.39 ^b
8	5.61±0.67 ^c	94.29±4.20 ^g	4.35±0.19 ^c	134.35±2.01 ^b	98.00±1.00 ^b	21.54±0.41 ^c
9	5.33±0.67 ^c	102.60±4.68 ^c	4.31±0.15 ^c	138.44±2.47 ^a	98.00±1.41 ^b	27.79±0.26 ^a
10	10.61±0.67 ^a	120.29±4.20 ^a	6.35±0.19 ^a	125.35±2.01 ^d	90.00±1.00 ^c	15.54±0.41 ^d
11	6.38±0.19 ^b	93.10±4.04 ^e	4.14±0.09 ^d	132.46±0.41 ^c	98.00±1.41 ^b	21.88±0.33 ^c

Means (±SEM) with different alphabetical superscripts in the same column are significantly different at P < 0.05.

Table 3.3. Effect of Formulated Diets on Lipid Profile of Diabetics Wistar Rats

Groups	TC(mmol/L)	TG(mmol/L)	HDL(mmol/L)	LDL(mmol/L)	VLDL(mmol/L)
1	1.96±0.20 b	1.25±0.06 c	1.41±0.26 b	0.98±0.09 b	0.22±0.02b
2	1.76±0.12 ^c	1.33±0.07 ^b	1.64±0.26 ^a	0.84±0.13 ^d	0.20±0.03 ^b
3	1.98±0.06 ^b	1.19±0.08 ^d	0.91±0.23 ^c	0.98±0.12 ^b	0.21±0.03 ^b
4	1.75±0.14 ^c	1.19±0.07 ^d	1.23±0.06 ^d	0.98±0.14 ^b	0.22±0.15 ^b
5	1.37±0.26 ^d	1.37±0.04 ^b	1.17±0.17 ^d	0.83±0.13 ^d	0.15±0.05 ^b
6	2.09±0.13 ^b	1.19±0.05 ^d	1.31±0.18 ^c	0.88±0.12 ^c	0.15±0.02 ^b
7	1.89±0.12 ^b	1.27±0.07 ^c	1.23±0.10 ^c	1.00±0.11 ^b	0.21±0.14 ^b
8	1.95±0.12 ^b	1.13±0.09 ^d	1.27±0.07 ^c	0.96±0.11 ^b	0.20±0.17 ^b
9	1.89±0.12 ^b	1.27±0.07 ^c	1.23±0.10 ^d	1.00±0.11 ^b	0.21±0.14 ^b
10	3.75±0.14 ^a	2.89±0.07 ^a	0.5±0.06 ^e	2.50±0.14 ^a	0.82±0.15 ^a
11	1.37±0.26 ^d	1.37±0.04 ^b	1.17±0.17 ^d	0.83±0.13 ^d	0.15±0.05 ^b

Means (±SEM) with different alphabetical superscripts in the same column are significantly

Table 3.4. Effect of Formulated Diets on Oxidative stress of Diabetic Wistar Rat

Groups	GSH(μmol/g tissue)	GPX(U/mg protein)	CAT(U/mg protein)
1	1.38±0.13 ^b	0.05±0.00 ^a	2.90±0.59 ^a
2	1.11±0.25 ^b	0.05±0.00 ^a	2.33±0.72 ^b
3	1.42±0.16 ^a	0.06±0.00 ^a	3.58±0.44 ^a
4	1.38±0.20 ^b	0.05±0.00 ^a	2.78±0.42 ^a
5	1.38±0.25 ^b	0.06±0.00 ^a	3.50±0.33 ^a
6	1.34±0.07 ^b	0.05±0.00 ^a	2.32±0.41 ^b
7	1.49±0.13 ^a	0.05±0.02 ^a	2.85±0.45 ^a
8	1.55±0.10 ^a	0.05±0.00 ^a	3.57±0.13 ^b
9	1.40±0.04 ^c	0.05±0.02 ^a	2.22±0.09 ^b
10	0.4±0.13 ^b	0.03±0.02 ^b	1.15±0.45 ^c
11	1.49±0.13 ^a	0.05±0.02 ^a	2.85±0.45 ^a

Means (±SEM) with different alphabetical superscripts in the same column are significantly different at P < 0.05.

4.0. DISCUSSION

This study demonstrated that the formulated diets exerted substantial protective effects against alloxan-induced biochemical alterations in diabetic Wistar rats. The elevated liver enzymes observed in the untreated diabetic group indicate hepatocellular injury resulting from oxidative stress and membrane damage induced by alloxan-generated reactive oxygen species. Similar elevations in AST, ALT, and ALP have been reported in experimental diabetic models (Ohaeri, 2001). The significant reductions in hepatic enzyme activities among rats fed the formulated diets suggest hepatoprotective effects of the dietary interventions. These improvements may be attributed to antioxidant phytochemicals, dietary fibre, vitamins, and minerals present in plantain, soybean, tigernut, and dates. Previous studies have demonstrated that plantain-based diets improve hepatic integrity in diabetic animals (Eleazu *et al.*, 2013). The elevated urea and creatinine levels observed in the diabetic control group indicate impaired renal function and possible diabetic nephropathy. Hyperglycaemia-induced oxidative stress has been implicated in renal tissue injury and reduced glomerular filtration rate in diabetes mellitus (Forbes & Cooper, 2013). Treatment with the formulated diets significantly reduced urea and creatinine concentrations, suggesting nephroprotective activity. Electrolyte imbalance observed in the untreated diabetic group reflects altered renal handling of ions and metabolic acidosis associated with uncontrolled diabetes. Restoration of sodium, chloride, and bicarbonate levels following dietary intervention suggests improved renal and metabolic regulation.

Diabetic dyslipidaemia observed in the untreated diabetic group is characterized by elevated cholesterol, triglycerides, LDL, and VLDL levels alongside reduced HDL concentration. These lipid abnormalities are common in insulin-deficient states and significantly contribute to cardiovascular complications (Goldberg, 2001). The hypolipidaemic effects demonstrated by the formulated diets may be linked to dietary fibre and phytochemical constituents capable of reducing intestinal lipid absorption and hepatic cholesterol synthesis.

Oxidative stress is a hallmark of diabetes mellitus and contributes substantially to the development of diabetic complications. The reduced antioxidant enzyme activities observed in the diabetic control group confirm depletion of endogenous antioxidant defense systems. Similar findings have been reported in previous studies involving alloxan-induced diabetic rats (Maritim *et al.*, 2003).

The significant improvements in GSH, GPx, and CAT activities among treated groups indicate enhanced antioxidant defense mechanisms. These antioxidant effects may be associated with phenolic compounds, vitamins, and bioactive phytochemicals present in the formulated diets, which help scavenge free radicals and reduce oxidative damage.

Overall, the findings suggest that the formulated diets possess significant antidiabetic, hepatoprotective, nephroprotective, hypolipidaemic, and antioxidant potentials.

5. CONCLUSION

This study demonstrated that locally formulated diets prepared from unripe plantain, soybean, tigernut, and dates significantly improved biochemical alterations associated with alloxan-induced diabetes mellitus in Wistar rats. The formulated diets effectively reduced hepatic enzyme activities, improved renal function and electrolyte balance, corrected dyslipidaemia, and enhanced antioxidant defense mechanisms. These findings indicate substantial hepatoprotective, nephroprotective, hypolipidaemic, and antioxidant properties of the formulated diets. The results further suggest that the formulated diets may serve as affordable and nutritionally beneficial functional foods for dietary management of diabetes mellitus and its associated complications.

Competing Interests

Authors have declared that they have no known competing financial interests or non-financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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